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Tail Risk from Extreme Temperature in an Integrated Northeastern American Low-Carbon Electricity System*

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Abstract

Cross-border electricity trade in the Northeastern American grid helps U.S. markets mitigate structural deficits in low-carbon generation capacity. These deficits are partially offset by surplus exports from Québec (hydropower) and Ontario (nuclear generation). We use a Vine copula to assess the nonlinear interdependence of these markets. Using hourly data from 2019-2023, we estimate the joint lower tail of regional net low-carbon surpluses. In the unconditional distribution, the 5% Value-at-Risk (VaR) indicates an aggregate deficit of -1.3% of low-carbon generation. Regional VaR estimates reveal pronounced asymmetries as U.S. shortfalls exceed local low-carbon generation by about 130–178%. While Canadian regions are substantially less exposed in the lower tail. On heat-wave days, the aggregate deficit is -1.8% with the U.S. regional shortfalls about 200–250%. As heat waves increase in frequency and intensity, there will be an increase reliance on fossil fuels during electricity shortfalls.

JEL classification: D24, F18, Q21, Q47, Q56

Keywords: Low-Carbon Electricity; Climate Resilience; Hydropower; Copula; Value at risk.

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1 Introduction

The increase in extreme weather events due to more hot or cold days will lead to more human mortality, see [Deschênes and Greenstone \(2011\)](#). To mitigate these adverse effects, there is an increase in electricity for cooling or heating. This increase in consumption of electricity has heterogeneous effects on households. [Doremus *et al.* \(2022\)](#) find that “*adaptation to extreme weather, such as air conditioning use, is prohibitively costly for households experiencing poverty.*” Therefore, the increase in electricity consumption raises the question of how it is generated and distributed. We study how risk management of electricity grids can be help us to mitigate potential adverse effects of extreme weather events.

Our study focus on the Northeastern American electricity market that spans Canada and the United States. Cross-border electricity market integration can generate two distinct gains for power systems when regions differ in their generation portfolios. It allows regions to share supply and demand imbalances and may lower the compliance costs of decarbonization. In the Northeastern American grid, Québec and Ontario operate predominantly low-carbon electricity systems based on hydropower and nuclear generation. In contrast, New York and New England rely more heavily on fossil-fuel generation and face persistent deficits in low-carbon supply. Canadian exports therefore help U.S. markets to mitigate structural shortfalls in low-carbon generation capacity, reducing fossil-fuel dispatch under normal conditions. The effectiveness of this cross-border adjustment, however, depends on the joint distribution of regional shocks and on the extent to which deficits are synchronized across borders.

A growing literature quantifies the benefits of electricity market integration. Transmission expansion reduces decarbonization costs and strengthens system adequacy under climate constraints ([Beiter *et al.*, 2017](#); [Fell and Linn, 2013](#); [Brinkman *et al.*, 2021](#)). More specifically, cross-border flows enable reciprocal load smoothing by exploiting geographic diversity ([Antweiler, 2016](#)). Similarly, European studies show that interconnection mitigates “energy droughts” associated with renewable variability ([Chen *et al.*, 2020](#)). However, these assessments generally rely on linear dependence structures or historical average conditions. As emphasized by [Otero *et al.* \(2022\)](#), such approaches may underestimate joint tail risks when severe weather events generate simultaneous deficits across interconnected regions.

This paper examines how extreme temperature events (heat and cold waves) affect the joint lower tail of regional net low-carbon electricity surpluses. Using hourly data from 2019 to 2023, we estimate a multivariate vine copula model to capture nonlinear and asymmetric dependence across regions. This framework allows us to quantify the likelihood and mag-

nititude of simultaneous shortfalls and to assess how conditioning on extreme temperature events alters aggregate low-carbon shortfall risk. The analysis is based on regional generation and load data. It therefore measures the joint availability of low-carbon supply relative to demand, rather than realized electricity flows or total supply adequacy.

We find a pronounced asymmetry in the behavior of the integrated system under extreme conditions. In the unconditional distribution, that is, when all days in the sample are considered without conditioning on extreme temperature events, structural low-carbon deficits appear in the lower tail. At the 5% Value-at-Risk (VaR) level, the aggregate deficit reaches -16 GW, corresponding to -1.3% of low-carbon generation. Although moderate at the aggregate level, regional VaR estimates reveal substantial heterogeneity. At the 5% level, U.S. shortfalls exceed local low-carbon generation by roughly 130-178%, whereas Canadian regions are considerably less exposed in the lower tail. Conditioning on heat-wave days deepens the aggregate deficit to -25.4 GW, corresponding to approximately -1.8% of low-carbon generation. While the change at the aggregate system level remains moderate in percentage terms, regional shortfalls intensify: U.S. deficits reach roughly 200-250% of local low-carbon generation, whereas Canadian low-carbon output remains broadly stable. In contrast, conditioning on cold-wave days leads to only a modest additional shift in aggregate low-carbon shortfall exposure.

These results indicate that cross-border integration improves the low-carbon balance of the interconnected system and provides meaningful stabilization. However, this stabilization remains partial during extreme events, particularly during synchronized heat waves. As heat waves become more frequent and intense, synchronized deficits may increase reliance on fossil-fuel generation in deficit-prone regions. In this context, strengthening low-carbon capacity and enhancing system flexibility would help preserve the decarbonization benefits of cross-border integration. Incorporating climate stress scenarios into adequacy assessments would reinforce these efforts by ensuring that resilience is evaluated under extreme temperature conditions. More broadly, our findings highlight the importance of evaluating interconnected power systems not only under average conditions, but also under joint tail shocks.

The remainder of the paper is organized as follows. Section 2 describes the data. Section 3 presents stylized facts. Section 4 outlines the empirical framework. Section 5 reports the results. Section 6 concludes.

2 Data from the Northeastern American grid

Our analysis focuses on the Northeastern American grid, a highly interconnected region characterized by heterogeneous generation portfolios. We examine four regions: the Canadian provinces of Ontario ([Independent Electricity System Operator or IESO](#)) and Québec ([Hydro-Québec](#)); and the U.S. markets of New York ([New York Independent System Operator or NYISO](#)) and the [Independent System Operator-New England or ISO-NE](#). Appendix Figure [A.1](#) illustrates the major cross-border transmission lines for the Northeastern North American grid.

We construct a harmonized hourly panel covering 2019-2023 using generation and load data from the respective Independent System Operators and balancing authorities. Reporting formats are standardized and all timestamps are converted to Coordinated Universal Time (UTC). After removing 0.67% of observations due to missing values, the final balanced panel contains 43,530 hourly observations for each region.

The central variable in our analysis is the *net low-carbon electricity surplus* (S_{it}), defined as:

$$S_{it} = G_{it}^{LC} - L_{it}, \tag{1}$$

where G_{it}^{LC} denotes generation from low-carbon sources (hydropower, nuclear, wind, solar, and biofuels) in region i at hour t , and L_{it} represents total electricity load in region i at hour t . A positive S_{it} indicates a surplus of low-carbon generation relative to local demand. A negative value implies a local deficit in low-carbon generation, requiring fossil-fuel dispatch and potential imports. The generation mix exhibits strong heterogeneity. As detailed in Section [3](#), Ontario and Québec rely predominantly on low-carbon sources, particularly hydropower and nuclear baseload generation, whereas New York and New England retain substantial fossil-fuel peaking capacity.

Our measure of net low-carbon surplus is an accounting construct based on regional generation and load. It does not model physical power flows, transmission constraints, or realized cross-border trade. Rather, it captures the availability of low-carbon generation relative to regional demand. As such, the analysis focuses on structural exposure to low-carbon shortfalls under joint regional stress, abstracting from the detailed allocation of electricity within broader interconnections.

We complement grid data with daily weather observations from the Global Historical Climatology Network-Daily (GHCNd). Using data from 294 World Meteorological Organiza-

tion (WMO) stations, we identify extreme temperature events following the climatological approach of Agel *et al.* (2021). A regional heat (cold) wave is defined as at least three consecutive days during which temperatures exceed the 95th (fall below the 5th) historical percentile and cross an absolute threshold of 32°C (−20°C). To capture localized stress that may trigger transmission constraints, we record a regional event if at least one monitoring station satisfies these criteria.

3 Stylized Facts

This section documents the structural heterogeneity underlying cross-border electricity trade in the region. Table 1 reports average load and generation by source.

Table 1: Fuel mix of electricity generation by region

	ON	QC	NY	NE
Total load	15.4	21.5	17.3	13.2
Total production	16.7	25.0	14.6	11.0
Low-carbon sources	15.1	24.4	7.8	5.0
Variable renewable sources	1.5	1.3	0.5	0.5
Fossil fuel sources	1.6	0.6	6.8	6.1

This table reports mean hourly total load and total production by source for Ontario (ON), Québec (QC), New York (NY), and New England (NE) over 2019–2023. Generation is classified into *low-carbon sources* (hydropower, nuclear, wind, solar, and biofuels) and *fossil-fuel sources* (natural gas, coal, and oil). *Variable renewable sources* (wind and solar) are reported as a subset of *low-carbon sources*.

Generation portfolios differ markedly across regions. Québec and Ontario rely predominantly on hydropower and nuclear generation and maintain persistent low-carbon surpluses. Québec exhibits an average surplus of 2.9 GW, while Ontario’s low-carbon supply is approximately balanced with demand. In contrast, New York and New England face structural deficits in low-carbon generation capacity averaging 9.5 GW and 8.2 GW, respectively. Low-carbon sources account for only 53% and 45% of total generation in these U.S. markets. Note the share of variable renewable resources are small share (10% or less) of low-carbon sources. The intermittency of these renewable sources and lack of storage have an implication for

grid resilience, see [Linn and Shih \(2019\)](#); [Pimm *et al.* \(2021\)](#); [Butters *et al.* \(2025\)](#). These differences imply sustained dependence on potential imports and fossil-fuel dispatch.

This asymmetry creates potential gains from trade when regional shocks are not perfectly correlated. [Table 2](#) reports pairwise correlations. Electricity demand is highly synchronized across Ontario, New York, and New England (0.82-0.94), reflecting common seasonal exposure. In contrast, Québec’s low-carbon surplus is negatively correlated with shortages in New York (−0.43) and New England (−0.41). This counter-cyclicality implies that Canadian surpluses, particularly from Québec, tend to be available when U.S. deficits are large, supporting cross-border adjustment under average conditions.

Table 2: Correlation across regions

	Low-carbon shortage			
	ON	QC	NY	NE
ON	.	-0.40	0.71	0.60
QC	0.50	.	-0.43	-0.41
NY	0.84	0.17	.	0.87
NE	0.82	0.31	0.94	.

The table reports pairwise Pearson correlations computed over hourly observations for Ontario (ON), Québec (QC), New York (NY), and New England (NE). The lower triangle reports correlations of electricity demand (*total load*). The upper triangle reports correlations of *low-carbon shortages*.

These patterns are closely linked to seasonal demand differences. [Figure 1](#) shows that while diurnal cycles (early-morning lows and afternoon peaks) are similar across regions, seasonal load profiles differ. U.S. regions experience pronounced summer peaks driven by cooling demand, which deepen their low-carbon shortfalls. Québec’s demand peaks in winter due to electric heating. As a result, Québec typically maintains low-carbon surpluses during periods of peak U.S. summer demand.

While these stylized facts describe average conditions, the resilience of this cross-border adjustment depends on the spatial distribution of extreme temperature events. [Appendix Figure A.2](#), shows that cold waves are concentrated in Canadian provinces during January and February, whereas heat waves occur more frequently in U.S. regions. Over 2019-2023, we identify 109 heat-wave days and 149 cold-wave days.

Figure 1: Seasonal patterns in load and low-carbon electricity surplus

The figure reports mean hourly load (left column) and net low-carbon electricity surplus (right column), measured in gigawatts (GW), for Ontario (ON), Québec (QC), New York (NY), and New England (NE) over 2019–2023. Panels (a) & (b) display average diurnal patterns, panels (c) & (d) average monthly patterns, and panels (e) & (f) annual averages.

(a) Load: Hour

(b) Surplus: Hour

(c) Load: Month

(d) Surplus: Month

(e) Load: Year

(f) Surplus: Year

— ON - · - QC
 - - - NY · · · NE

— ON - · - QC
 - - - NY · · · NE

These patterns suggest that cross-border trade can smooth regional imbalances under typical conditions. Linear correlations and seasonal averages do not capture joint lower-tail dependence under extreme temperature events. If extreme temperature events occur simultaneously across regions, the scope for cross-border adjustment may shrink precisely when it is most needed. We formalize this analysis within a multivariate vine copula framework.

4 Vine Copula and Value-at-Risk Analysis

The use of vine copulas for modeling the joint distribution of shocks in the context of Value-at-Risk (VaR) analysis is a robust method to capture the dependencies between different financial or operational risk factors. This approach is particularly useful in estimating the joint distribution of low-carbon shortage shocks.

The primary objective is to estimate the joint distribution of shocks associated with low-carbon electricity shortages. We employ Vine copulas (Aas *et al.*, 2009) as they provide a framework particularly suited to this context. Unlike the elliptical and largely linear dependence implied by standard multivariate normal or t-distributions, Vine copulas allow for asymmetric tail dependence. This flexibility is economically critical: given that the consequences of climate shocks are dominated by rare joint shortfalls, a model that fails to capture tail co-movements would systematically understate the risk of simultaneous deficits. Furthermore, the vine structure allows the dependence between any pair of regions to vary conditionally, mirroring how network constraints and market tightness jointly shape cross-border risk pooling.

4.1 Accounting for trends, seasonality, and other temporal effects

To prepare the data for analysis, the hourly time series data is demeaned to remove seasonal patterns and other temporal effects. Specifically, the data is adjusted by year, month, and the interaction of weekday and hour. This detrending helps in isolating the stochastic components of the time series, which are more relevant for risk modeling:

$$X_{t,\text{demeaned}} = X_t - \mathbb{E}(X_t \mid \text{year, month, weekday} \times \text{hour}). \quad (2)$$

This step is important for ensuring that the subsequent analysis focuses on the inherent variability in the data rather than predictable seasonal effects (Tsay, 2005). Next, each

time series of shocks is modeled using an ARMA(1,1) process to capture the autocorrelation structure, combined with a GARCH(1,1) process to model volatility clustering. This helps in understanding the conditional mean and variance of the shocks:

$$\begin{aligned} X_t &= \phi_0 + \phi_1 X_{t-1} + \theta_1 \epsilon_{t-1} + \epsilon_t, \\ \epsilon_t | \mathcal{F}_{t-1} &\sim \mathcal{N}(0, \sigma_t^2), \quad \sigma_t^2 = \alpha_0 + \alpha_1 \epsilon_{t-1}^2 + \beta_1 \sigma_{t-1}^2. \end{aligned} \tag{3}$$

This method, as described by [McNeil *et al.* \(2015\)](#), is effective in capturing the time-varying volatility observed in financial time series data. The ARMA component models the autocorrelation in the series, while the GARCH component captures the volatility clustering, which is a common feature in financial time series ([Bollerslev, 1986](#)).

4.2 Vine copula

The residuals from the ARMA-GARCH model (3) are standardized and then fitted using a regular vine copula (R-vine). This copula structure allows for flexible modeling of the dependency structure between multiple variables by decomposing the multivariate distribution into a cascade of bivariate copulas. The R-vine copula is particularly useful because it does not assume a specific form for the multivariate distribution but instead constructs it from a series of bivariate copulas. This flexibility allows for a more accurate representation of complex dependency structures ([Czado, 2010](#)).

Different copula families are considered to capture different types of dependencies: Gaussian Copula (Captures linear dependencies), Student-t Copula (Captures linear dependencies with tail dependence), Clayton Copula (Captures lower tail dependence), Gumbel Copula (Captures upper tail dependence), Frank Copula (Suitable for moderate dependencies), and Joe Copula (Captures upper tail dependence with a different structure than Gumbel). These copula families are discussed in depth by [Joe \(1997\)](#), who provides a comprehensive overview of their properties and applications. The choice of copula family depends on the specific characteristics of the dependencies in the data being modeled. For instance, the Student-t copula is often used when there is evidence of tail dependence, which is a common feature in financial data ([Demarta and McNeil, 2005](#)).

For each pair of variables, the best-fitting copula model is selected using the Akaike Information Criterion (AIC) which balances model complexity and goodness of fit: $AIC = 2k - 2 \log(L)$, where k is the number of parameters and L is the likelihood. The AIC is a widely used measure for model selection, providing a balance between goodness of fit and

model complexity. By minimizing the AIC, we select models that provide a good fit to the data without overfitting (Akaike, 1974).

The overall vine structure, which determines the order in which the bivariate copulas are combined, is based on the absolute values of the empirical Kendall’s tau. Kendall’s tau is a measure of rank correlation, which evaluates the strength and direction of association between two variables. It is defined as:

$$\tau = \frac{2}{n(n-1)} \sum_{i < j} \text{sign}(x_i - x_j) \text{sign}(y_i - y_j). \quad (4)$$

Kendall’s tau ranges from -1 to 1, where 1 indicates a perfect positive association, -1 indicates a perfect negative association, and 0 indicates no association. This measure is particularly useful for constructing vine copulas for several reasons: robustness to outliers (as a rank-based measure, Kendall’s tau is less sensitive to outliers compared to correlation coefficients that rely on raw data values), non-parametric nature (it does not assume any specific distribution for the data, making it broadly applicable), interpretability (the values of Kendall’s tau provide a clear interpretation of the dependence strength between pairs of variables).

Using Kendall’s tau to determine the vine structure ensures that the copula model accurately captures the underlying dependencies in the data. This approach, as highlighted by Patton (2006), allows for the creation of a flexible and robust multivariate model that can handle complex dependencies between variables.¹

5 Results

The seasonal asymmetries documented in Section 3 raise the question of whether interconnection provides effective risk sharing during extreme temperature events. Deschênes and Greenstone (2011) find that “*climate change will lead to an increase of 3% in the age-adjusted mortality rate and about 11% in annual residential energy consumption.*” In addition, Doremus *et al.* (2022) find that increase in cooling becomes prohibitive expensive for low-income households. Therefore, understanding electricity grid supply and the distribution during extreme temperature events is a first-order importance. We address this by conditioning the Value-at-Risk (VaR) analysis on regional heat and cold-wave periods.

¹Additional details are provided in Appendix A. Table A.1 and Figure A.3 present the copula selection criteria and goodness-of-fit diagnostics, while Table A.2 reports the unconditional VaR and ES estimates that serve as benchmarks for the climate stress analysis.

Table 3 reports correlations in the occurrence of heat and cold waves. Unlike the average seasonal patterns described above, these correlations capture synchronization during extreme temperature events. Heat waves display strong within-country synchronization. The correlation between New York (NY) and New England (NE) reaches 0.72, while Ontario (ON) and Québec (QC) exhibit a correlation of 0.54. Cross-border correlations are positive but smaller, averaging around 0.32 between Canadian and U.S. regions. These patterns indicate that heat waves frequently affect multiple regions simultaneously, reducing the scope for geographic diversification during extreme temperature episodes. Cold waves exhibit a different structure. Within-country correlations remain relatively high only between Ontario and Québec (0.613). Cross-border correlations are more uneven. For example, the correlation between New York and Québec is only 0.099, whereas correlations between New England and Canadian provinces are around 0.36. This heterogeneity suggests that cold-wave synchronization varies across regions and may preserve some scope for geographic diversification.

Table 3: Correlation of regional heat and cold waves

Heat Wave				
	ON	QC	NY	NE
ON		0.544	0.344	0.211
QC	0.613		0.324	0.326
NY	0.212	0.099		0.720
NE	0.396	0.360	0.360	
Cold Wave				
	ON	QC	NY	NE

The table reports pairwise correlations of regional heat-wave and cold-wave occurrences for Ontario (ON), Québec (QC), New York (NY), and New England (NE) over 2019-2023. The upper triangle reports correlations of heat waves, and the lower triangle reports correlations of cold waves.

We next examine how these physical patterns translate into economic risk. Table 4 reports the VaR and Expected Shortfall (ES) of the aggregate low-carbon surplus. Under the unconditional distribution (*Overall*), i.e., when all days in the sample are considered without conditioning on extreme temperature events, the 5% VaR deficit equals -16.1 GW. This corresponds to -1.3% of low-carbon generation.

Table 4: Estimated risk levels for net low-carbon electricity surplus under extreme weather in gigawatts (GW) and as a percentage of low-carbon generation (%)

	P25	Median	Mean	P75
<i>Overall</i>				
VaR at 5%	-19.2	-14.8	-15.8	-11.3
<i>in %</i>	-1.4%	-1.3%	-1.3%	-1.1%
ES at 5%	-19.5	-15.1	-16.1	-11.6
<i>in %</i>	-2.0%	-1.8%	-1.8%	-1.6%
<i>Heat-wave days</i>				
VaR at 5%	-31.7	-25.0	-25.4	-19.1
<i>in %</i>	-2.0%	-1.8%	-1.8%	-1.6%
ES at 5%	-32.0	-25.3	-25.6	-19.3
<i>in %</i>	-2.6%	-2.3%	-2.4%	-2.1%
<i>Cold-wave days</i>				
VaR at 5%	-21.3	-17.6	-17.8	-13.9
<i>in %</i>	-1.6%	-1.5%	-1.5%	-1.3%
ES at 5%	-21.6	-17.9	-18.1	-14.1
<i>in %</i>	-2.1%	-1.9%	-1.9%	-1.7%

The table reports Value-at-Risk (VaR) and Expected Shortfall (ES) estimates for the aggregate net low-carbon electricity surplus in the Northeastern region. Results are shown for the unconditional distribution (*Overall*), i.e., without conditioning on extreme temperature events, and conditional on *heat-wave days* and *cold-wave days*. Risk levels are reported in gigawatts (GW) and, directly below, as a percentage of contemporaneous aggregate low-carbon generation. Negative values indicate a low-carbon electricity deficit relative to demand. Appendix A Tables A.3, A.5, and A.7 report the corresponding regional VaR and ES estimates in levels and percentages under the unconditional distribution and under heat-wave and cold-wave conditions.

Although the aggregate deficit is moderate in magnitude, regional VaR estimates reveal substantial heterogeneity.² The relatively limited aggregate deficit is consistent with imperfect

²Tables A.3 and A.4, at the 5% level, shortfalls in New York and New England correspond to 130% (-9.82 GW) and 178% (-8.57 GW) of their respective low-carbon generation, implying significant reliance on fossil-fuel generation and potential imports. In contrast, Québec maintains a positive low-carbon surplus of 2.44 GW at the 5% VaR level, while Ontario records a small deficit of -0.67 GW.

synchronization of regional tail risk: Canadian surpluses partly offset U.S. shortfalls, but not sufficiently to prevent a system-wide deficit.

During heat waves, as reported in Table 4, aggregate low-carbon shortfall risk increases. Consistent with the positive cross-regional correlations documented in Table 3, extreme heat is associated with synchronized market tightness across regions.

The 5% VaR deficit rises to -25.4 GW, while the Expected Shortfall reaches -25.6 GW. The effect is most pronounced in the lower tail of the conditional distribution. In the worst quartile of heat-wave outcomes (the 25th percentile), the system-wide deficit deepens to -31.7 GW. These results indicate that conditioning on heat-wave days shifts the lower tail of the distribution toward larger simultaneous regional shortfalls.

Expressed as a share of contemporaneous low-carbon generation, the aggregate 5% VaR reaches -1.8% , compared with -1.3% in the unconditional distribution. The change at the aggregate level therefore remains moderate in percentage terms. However, this aggregation masks substantial regional heterogeneity. As reported in Appendix Tables A.5 and A.6, the 5% VaR deficit in New York widens from -9.82 GW in the unconditional distribution to -14.72 GW during heat-wave days, corresponding to nearly a 200% low-carbon generation deficit. In New England, the deficit increases from -8.57 GW to -12.25 GW, exceeding 250% of local low-carbon generation. In contrast, Ontario's deficit deepens more modestly from -0.67 GW to -2.68 GW, while Québec's low-carbon positive surplus remains broadly stable. Results suggest that the deterioration in aggregate tail risk during heat waves is largely associated with intensified U.S. shortfalls rather than with a contraction of Canadian surplus. This implies greater reliance on fossil-fuel generation and potential imports from surplus regions during extreme heat.

In contrast, as reported in Table 4, cold waves generate a more moderate increase in aggregate low-carbon shortfall risk. At the 5% VaR level, the aggregate deficit widens from -15.84 GW under the unconditional distribution to -17.78 GW (-1.5% of low-carbon generation). Appendix Table A.7 and Table A.8, regional effects are comparatively smaller than during heat waves. Deficits in New York deepen from -9.82 GW to -10.51 GW (133% of low-carbon generation), and in New England from -8.57 GW to -9.34 GW (170% of low-carbon generation). Ontario's deficit deepens from -0.67 GW to -1.55 GW, while Québec maintains a similar positive surplus. Compared to heat waves, where the aggregate deficit expands by 9.5 GW, the cold-wave negative effect remains limited. The quantitative increase in U.S. shortfalls is modest, and the conditional distribution shifts only slightly relative to

the unconditional one.³

Taken together, the results show that structural low-carbon deficits are already present in the lower tail of the unconditional distribution. Conditioning on heat-wave days shifts this lower tail toward larger aggregate deficits, whereas conditioning on cold-wave days leads to only a modest additional change. This contrast indicates that synchronized heat waves intensify existing shortfalls, while cold waves do not generate comparable aggregate stress. These aggregate dynamics are primarily driven by large U.S. deficits in the lower tail, which are only partially offset by Canadian surpluses. Québec, in particular, maintains a positive low-carbon surplus across temperature regimes, consistent with the flexibility of its predominantly hydro-based generation mix.

This lack of capacity leads to issues of resilience and decarbonization in the U.S. Recent work by [Kiesling *et al.* \(2026\)](#) has found that since the mid-1990s there was a 32% decrease in carbon due to the changing electricity generation mix in the U.S. They point to wholesale power markets as a catalyst for the transition away from coal towards primarily natural gas. However, the level of decarbonization has leveled off since the early 2010s. so, to continue decarbonization would require policy actions towards further substitution to renewables.

6 Conclusion

This paper evaluates the resilience of cross-border electricity integration in the Northeastern North American grid under extreme temperature events. Using a multivariate vine copula model, we estimate the joint lower tail of regional low-carbon surpluses and quantify how heat and cold waves modify aggregate low-carbon shortfall risk.

Structural low-carbon deficits are already present in the lower tail of the unconditional distribution, that is, when all days are considered without conditioning on extreme events. At the 5% Value-at-Risk (VaR) level, the aggregate deficit reaches -16 GW (-1.3% of low-carbon generation). While moderate at the system level, regional exposures are markedly asymmetric: lower-tail deficits in U.S. markets correspond to roughly 130-178% of their local low-carbon generation, whereas Canadian outcomes remain comparatively stable. The aggregate shortfall therefore reflects only a partial offset between structurally asymmetric regional exposures. Conditioning on heat-wave days deepens the 5% VaR deficit to -25.4 GW

³Appendix Tables [A.3](#) and [A.4](#), we report robustness results using the 10% Value-at-Risk (VaR) and corresponding Expected Shortfall (ES) of the aggregate low-carbon surplus. Overall, results remain qualitatively similar.

(-1.8%). U.S. shortfalls rise to roughly 200-250% of local low-carbon generation, whereas Canadian net positions remain broadly stable. By contrast, conditioning on cold-wave days produces only a limited additional shift in aggregate exposure relative to the unconditional distribution.

Our results illustrate that cross-border integration improves the low-carbon balance of the interconnected system and provides meaningful stabilization. However, its capacity to offset synchronized shortfalls remains quantitatively limited during extreme heat, when deficits become more strongly aligned across regions.

These findings have three implications for energy policy and infrastructure planning. First, cross-border integration remains an important mechanism for reducing structural low-carbon imbalances across regions. Second, adequacy assessments based solely on unconditional distributions may understate exposure to synchronized climate stress. Third, maintaining reliability and limiting carbon intensity in a warming climate cannot rely exclusively on existing transmission links. If extreme heat becomes more frequent or intense, additional low-carbon capacity and greater system flexibility in deficit-prone regions will be necessary to prevent increased reliance on fossil-fuel generation.

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Appendix

This appendix provides background information on figures and tables. In addition, it provides robustness on the econometric models and reports supporting risk estimates. It complements the main analysis by presenting: (i) the specification and goodness-of-fit of the vine copula; (ii) the distributional properties of simulated shocks; (iii) baseline Value-at-Risk (VaR) and Expected Shortfall (ES) estimates under the unconditional distribution; and conditional VaR and ES estimates under (iv) heat-wave and (v) cold-wave days.

A.1: The Northeastern American interchange transmission lines

Figure A.1 displays major interchange transmission lines in North America.

Figure A.1: Major interchange transmission lines in North America

Source: U.S. Energy Information Administration (EIA).

The figure shows high-voltage interchange transmission lines across North America. In the Northeastern corridor, the main cross-border interfaces connect Ontario (IESO) and Québec (Hydro-Québec) with New York (NYISO), New England (ISO-NE), and the Midwest (MISO). These interfaces account for the dominant Canadian electricity exports to the Northeastern United States.

In the Northeastern corridor, Ontario and Québec account for the largest Canadian electricity exports to U.S. markets in New York (NYISO) and New England (ISO-NE). According to the U.S. Energy Information Administration ([U.S. Energy Information Administration](#),

2024), in 2022 Ontario’s net electricity exports averaged 23 GWh per day to the Midwest (MISO) and 14 GWh per day to New York (NYISO). Over the same period, Hydro-Québec supplied on average 37 GWh per day to New England (ISO-NE) and 25 GWh per day to New York (NYISO). By comparison, exchanges from New Brunswick to New England (ISO-NE) averaged approximately 5.5 GWh per day. These figures indicate that the dominant cross-border electricity flows into the Northeastern U.S. markets originate from Ontario and Québec, which correspond to the regions analyzed in this paper.

A.2: Distribution of regional heat and cold-wave events

Figure A.2 details the monthly frequency of extreme temperature events across the four regions.

Figure A.2: Average regional heat-wave and cold-wave days

(a) Number of heat-wave days

(b) Number of cold-wave days

The figure reports the average monthly number of regional heat-wave and cold-wave days over 2019-2023. Panels (a) and (b) display heat-wave and cold-wave frequencies, respectively.

The data indicate a strong seasonal concentration: heat waves occur predominantly dur-

ing summer months (June-August) and are more frequent in New York and New England, whereas cold waves occur mainly during winter months (January-February) and are more common in Ontario and Québec.

A.3: Robustness of the Dependence Structure

Table A.1 reports the pairwise copula families selected for the D-vine decomposition based on the Akaike Information Criterion (AIC). Student- t copulas are selected for all pairs. Unlike Gaussian copulas, the Student- t specification allows for asymptotic tail dependence. This result indicates that regional low-carbon balances exhibit joint extreme deviations more frequently than implied by a normal dependence structure. The goodness-of-fit statistics (log-likelihood and AIC/BIC) further support the adequacy of this heavy-tailed specification in capturing the dependence between Canadian surpluses and U.S. deficits.

Figure A.3 illustrates these dependencies through bivariate density contours, highlighting the shape of the joint distributions underlying the simulations.

Table A.1: Estimated vine copula structure

Edge	Copula	Corr (ρ)	DF (ν)	Kendall's τ	Upper-tail	Lower-tail
QC, ON	t	-0.32	8.52	-0.20	0.00	0.00
NY, QC	t	-0.21	17.52	-0.13	0.00	0.00
NE, NY	t	0.27	10.81	0.17	0.02	0.02
NY, ON; QC	t	0.07	11.07	0.04	0.01	0.01
NE, QC; NY	t	-0.05	18.47	-0.03	0.00	0.00
NE, ON; NY, QC	t	0.08	27.22	0.05	0.00	0.00

The table reports the estimated pair-copula families and parameters for the D-vine specification of regional net low-carbon electricity surpluses over 2019-2023. Corr (ρ) denotes the linear correlation parameter, DF (ν) the degrees of freedom, and Kendall's τ the implied rank correlation. Upper- and lower-tail coefficients report tail dependence measures. The consistent selection of Student- t copulas indicates the presence of tail dependence across regions. Log-likelihood: 5862.26; AIC: -11700.53; BIC: -11596.35.

Figure A.3: Vine copula density contours

The figure displays the bivariate density contours of the standardized residuals for the first tree of the D-vine specification of regional net low-carbon electricity surpluses. Regions are indexed as follows: Ontario (ON) = 1, Québec (QC) = 2, New York (NY) = 3, and New England (NE) = 4.

A.4: Distribution of Simulated Shocks

Table A.2 reports summary statistics of the stochastic shocks generated by the vine copula model. These shocks capture the residual variability of low-carbon surpluses after controlling for seasonal and autoregressive components. The decline in the mean total shock from -0.67 GW at the 10% VaR level to -0.86 GW at the 5% VaR level reflects a progressive deepening of aggregate low-carbon shortfalls in the lower tail of the joint distribution, even prior to conditioning on extreme temperature events.

Table A.2: Summary statistics of simulated shocks to low-carbon electricity surplus (GW)

	10% Value-at-Risk (VaR)							
	10% Value-at-Risk (VaR)				Expected Shortfall (ES)			
	P25	Median	Mean	P75	P25	Median	Mean	P75
ON	-0.40	-0.37	-0.37	-0.34	-0.54	-0.50	-0.51	-0.47
QC	-0.50	-0.44	-0.46	-0.39	-0.69	-0.60	-0.63	-0.53
NY	-0.34	-0.31	-0.32	-0.28	-0.46	-0.43	-0.44	-0.39
NE	-0.33	-0.30	-0.31	-0.28	-0.45	-0.42	-0.42	-0.38
Total	-0.72	-0.66	-0.67	-0.60	-1.01	-0.93	-0.94	-0.86

	5% Value-at-Risk (VaR)							
	5% Value-at-Risk (VaR)				Expected Shortfall (ES)			
	P25	Median	Mean	P75	P25	Median	Mean	P75
ON	-0.51	-0.47	-0.47	-0.43	-0.64	-0.59	-0.59	-0.54
QC	-0.64	-0.56	-0.58	-0.49	-0.81	-0.70	-0.73	-0.62
NY	-0.43	-0.40	-0.41	-0.36	-0.55	-0.50	-0.51	-0.46
NE	-0.42	-0.39	-0.39	-0.36	-0.53	-0.49	-0.50	-0.45
Total	-0.93	-0.85	-0.86	-0.78	-1.20	-1.10	-1.12	-1.01

The table reports summary statistics of simulated shocks to net low-carbon electricity surplus, measured in gigawatts (GW), for Ontario (ON), Québec (QC), New York (NY), and New England (NE) over 2019-2023. Statistics are computed at the 10% and 5% Value-at-Risk (VaR) levels and include the corresponding Expected Shortfall (ES). Negative values indicate deficits relative to electricity demand.

A.5: Unconditional Risk by Region

This subsection reports VaR and ES estimates under the unconditional distribution, that is, when all days in the sample are considered without conditioning on heat or cold waves. These estimates capture the structural exposure of the grid to low-carbon shortages implied by the joint distribution of regional net surpluses. The aggregate figures reported here are consistent with those presented in Section 5, Table 4, for the unconditional distribution. Tables A.3 and A.4 present unconditional risk levels in absolute gigawatt terms (GW) and as a share of contemporaneous low-carbon generation (%), respectively.

Table A.3: Estimated risk levels for net low-carbon electricity surplus (GW)

	10% Value-at-Risk (VaR)							
	10% Value-at-Risk (VaR)				Expected Shortfall (ES)			
	P25	Median	Mean	P75	P25	Median	Mean	P75
ON	-2.15	-0.58	-0.77	0.84	-2.27	-0.70	-0.90	0.72
QC	1.18	2.48	2.31	3.63	1.04	2.33	2.16	3.48
NY	-11.44	-9.45	-9.91	-7.82	-11.55	-9.56	-10.01	-7.92
NE	-9.95	-8.37	-8.66	-7.01	-10.06	-8.47	-8.76	-7.11
Total	-19.38	-15.00	-16.04	-11.53	-19.63	-15.26	-16.30	-11.79

	5% Value-at-Risk (VaR)							
	5% Value-at-Risk (VaR)				Expected Shortfall (ES)			
	P25	Median	Mean	P75	P25	Median	Mean	P75
ON	-2.05	-0.48	-0.67	0.94	-2.19	-0.61	-0.81	0.80
QC	1.31	2.61	2.44	3.76	1.14	2.44	2.27	3.59
NY	-11.35	-9.36	-9.82	-7.73	-11.47	-9.48	-9.94	-7.85
NE	-9.86	-8.29	-8.57	-6.92	-9.98	-8.40	-8.69	-7.04
Total	-19.18	-14.81	-15.84	-11.33	-19.45	-15.08	-16.12	-11.61

The table reports regional Value-at-Risk (VaR) and Expected Shortfall (ES) estimates for net low-carbon electricity surplus under the unconditional distribution, measured in gigawatts (GW), for Ontario (ON), Québec (QC), New York (NY), and New England (NE). Results are shown at the 10% and 5% VaR levels. Negative values indicate low-carbon generation deficits relative to electricity demand, requiring imports and/or fossil-fuel generation.

Table A.4: Estimated risk levels for net low-carbon electricity surplus (% of low-carbon generation)

10% Value-at-Risk (VaR)								
	10% Value-at-Risk (VaR)				Expected Shortfall (ES)			
	P25	Median	Mean	P75	P25	Median	Mean	P75
ON	-14.4%	-3.8%	-5.4%	5.4%	-15.2%	-4.6%	-6.2%	4.7%
QC	5.2%	9.9%	9.1%	13.7%	4.6%	9.3%	8.5%	13.1%
NY	-157.0%	-124.9%	-131.0%	-97.5%	-158.4%	-126.3%	-132.4%	-98.7%
NE	-213.0%	-168.5%	-179.8%	-136.5%	-215.3%	-170.5%	-182.0%	-138.5%
Total	-1.9%	-1.6%	-1.7%	-1.5%	-2.4%	-2.1%	-2.2%	-1.9%

5% Value-at-Risk (VaR)								
	5% Value-at-Risk (VaR)				Expected Shortfall (ES)			
	P25	Median	Mean	P75	P25	Median	Mean	P75
ON	-13.7%	-3.1%	-4.7%	6.1%	-14.6%	-4.0%	-5.6%	5.2%
QC	5.8%	10.4%	9.6%	14.1%	5.0%	9.7%	8.9%	13.5%
NY	-155.7%	-123.7%	-129.9%	-96.4%	-157.4%	-125.3%	-131.4%	-97.9%
NE	-211.2%	-166.8%	-178.1%	-134.9%	-213.7%	-169.1%	-180.5%	-137.1%
Total	-1.4%	-1.3%	-1.3%	-1.1%	-2.0%	-1.8%	-1.8%	-1.6%

The table reports regional Value-at-Risk (VaR) and Expected Shortfall (ES) estimates for net low-carbon electricity surplus under the unconditional distribution, expressed as a share of contemporaneous low-carbon generation. Results are shown at the 10% and 5% VaR levels. Negative values indicate low-carbon deficits requiring imports and/or fossil-fuel generation. Values below -100% indicate deficits exceeding contemporaneous local low-carbon generation.

A.6: Heat Wave Risk by Region

This subsection reports VaR and ES estimates conditional on heat-wave days only. These estimates characterize the distribution of low-carbon surpluses during periods of extreme high temperatures, as defined in Section 2. The aggregate figures reported here are consistent with those presented in Section 5, Table 4, for heat-wave days. Tables A.5 and A.6 report conditional risk levels in absolute gigawatt terms (GW) and as a share of contemporaneous low-carbon generation (%), respectively.

Table A.5: Estimated risk levels for net low-carbon electricity surplus under heat-wave days (GW)

10% Value-at-Risk (VaR)								
	10% Value-at-Risk (VaR)				Expected Shortfall (ES)			
	P25	Median	Mean	P75	P25	Median	Mean	P75
ON	-4.50	-2.56	-2.57	-0.61	-4.65	-2.69	-2.72	-0.74
QC	2.58	3.84	3.39	4.62	2.43	3.69	3.23	4.45
NY	-17.55	-14.55	-14.62	-11.66	-17.68	-14.68	-14.76	-11.79
NE	-14.57	-11.97	-12.16	-9.64	-14.71	-12.08	-12.28	-9.77
Total	-31.45	-24.78	-25.16	-18.85	-31.77	-25.12	-25.45	-19.12

5% Value-at-Risk (VaR)								
	5% Value-at-Risk (VaR)				Expected Shortfall (ES)			
	P25	Median	Mean	P75	P25	Median	Mean	P75
ON	-4.61	-2.66	-2.68	-0.71	-4.75	-2.78	-2.81	-0.82
QC	2.47	3.73	3.27	4.49	2.33	3.58	3.13	4.35
NY	-17.65	-14.64	-14.72	-11.76	-17.76	-14.77	-14.84	-11.86
NE	-14.68	-12.06	-12.25	-9.74	-14.78	-12.15	-12.36	-9.84
Total	-31.66	-25.03	-25.37	-19.05	-31.95	-25.27	-25.63	-19.30

The table reports regional Value-at-Risk (VaR) and Expected Shortfall (ES) estimates for net low-carbon electricity surplus conditional on heat-wave days, measured in gigawatts (GW), for Ontario (ON), Québec (QC), New York (NY), and New England (NE). Results are shown at the 10% and 5% VaR levels.

Negative values indicate low-carbon generation deficits relative to electricity demand, requiring imports and/or fossil-fuel generation.

Table A.6: Estimated risk levels for net low-carbon electricity surplus under heat-wave days (% of low-carbon generation)

10% Value-at-Risk (VaR)								
	10% Value-at-Risk (VaR)				Expected Shortfall (ES)			
	P25	Median	Mean	P75	P25	Median	Mean	P75
ON	-29.4%	-16.6%	-16.7%	-3.9%	-30.3%	-17.5%	-17.7%	-4.6%
QC	13.2%	17.1%	15.0%	19.5%	12.3%	16.4%	14.2%	18.8%
NY	-228.5%	-195.2%	-196.0%	-159.1%	-230.3%	-196.9%	-197.7%	-160.8%
NE	-294.8%	-260.8%	-256.7%	-217.3%	-297.6%	-263.2%	-259.4%	-219.6%
Total	-1.5%	-1.4%	-1.4%	-1.3%	-2.2%	-2.0%	-2.0%	-1.8%

5% Value-at-Risk (VaR)								
	5% Value-at-Risk (VaR)				Expected Shortfall (ES)			
	P25	Median	Mean	P75	P25	Median	Mean	P75
ON	-30.1%	-17.3%	-17.4%	-4.4%	-31.0%	-18.0%	-18.3%	-5.2%
QC	12.6%	16.6%	14.4%	19.0%	11.8%	16.0%	13.7%	18.4%
NY	-229.9%	-196.4%	-197.3%	-160.4%	-231.2%	-197.9%	-198.8%	-161.9%
NE	-297.0%	-262.6%	-258.7%	-219.1%	-299.1%	-264.9%	-261.1%	-221.1%
Total	-2.0%	-1.8%	-1.8%	-1.6%	-2.6%	-2.3%	-2.4%	-2.1%

The table reports regional Value-at-Risk (VaR) and Expected Shortfall (ES) estimates for net low-carbon electricity surplus conditional on heat-wave days, expressed as a share of contemporaneous low-carbon generation. Results are shown at the 10% and 5% VaR levels. Negative values indicate low-carbon deficits requiring imports and/or fossil-fuel generation. Values below -100% indicate deficits exceeding contemporaneous local low-carbon generation.

A.7: Cold Wave Risk by Region

This subsection reports VaR and ES estimates conditional on cold-wave days only. These estimates characterize the distribution of low-carbon surpluses during periods of extreme low temperatures, as defined in Section 2. The aggregate figures reported here are consistent with those presented in Section 5, Table 4, for cold-wave days. Tables A.7 and A.8 present conditional risk levels in absolute gigawatt terms (GW) and as a share of contemporaneous

low-carbon generation (%), respectively.

Table A.7: Estimated risk levels for net low-carbon electricity surplus under cold-wave days (GW)

10% Value-at-Risk (VaR)								
	10% Value-at-Risk (VaR)				Expected Shortfall (ES)			
	P25	Median	Mean	P75	P25	Median	Mean	P75
ON	-2.69	-1.52	-1.45	-0.22	-2.83	-1.66	-1.59	-0.37
QC	1.77	2.92	2.70	3.90	1.54	2.71	2.49	3.71
NY	-11.87	-10.47	-10.42	-9.10	-12.00	-10.59	-10.54	-9.21
NE	-10.48	-9.25	-9.26	-8.02	-10.60	-9.36	-9.37	-8.13
Total	-21.04	-17.42	-17.56	-13.68	-21.36	-17.72	-17.86	-13.96

5% Value-at-Risk (VaR)								
	5% Value-at-Risk (VaR)				Expected Shortfall (ES)			
	P25	Median	Mean	P75	P25	Median	Mean	P75
ON	-2.81	-1.62	-1.55	-0.33	-2.93	-1.75	-1.68	-0.46
QC	1.61	2.76	2.54	3.75	1.39	2.57	2.35	3.59
NY	-11.97	-10.57	-10.51	-9.18	-12.07	-10.67	-10.62	-9.29
NE	-10.57	-9.33	-9.34	-8.09	-10.67	-9.43	-9.45	-8.20
Total	-21.28	-17.64	-17.78	-13.88	-21.59	-17.93	-18.05	-14.15

The table reports regional Value-at-Risk (VaR) and Expected Shortfall (ES) estimates for net low-carbon electricity surplus conditional on cold-wave days, measured in gigawatts (GW), for Ontario (ON), Québec (QC), New York (NY), and New England (NE). Results are shown at the 10% and 5% VaR levels.

Negative values indicate low-carbon generation deficits relative to electricity demand, requiring imports and/or fossil-fuel generation.

Table A.8: Estimated risk levels for net low-carbon electricity surplus under cold-wave days (% of low-carbon generation)

10% Value-at-Risk (VaR)								
	10% Value-at-Risk (VaR)				Expected Shortfall (ES)			
	P25	Median	Mean	P75	P25	Median	Mean	P75
ON	-17.6%	-9.3%	-9.4%	-1.4%	-18.6%	-10.2%	-10.3%	-2.3%
QC	5.4%	8.8%	8.1%	11.5%	4.7%	8.1%	7.4%	11.0%
NY	-154.5%	-132.1%	-131.4%	-106.6%	-156.1%	-133.6%	-132.9%	-108.0%
NE	-189.9%	-163.3%	-168.0%	-140.6%	-192.1%	-165.4%	-170.1%	-142.5%
Total	-1.3%	-1.1%	-1.1%	-1.0%	-1.8%	-1.6%	-1.6%	-1.4%

5% Value-at-Risk (VaR)								
	5% Value-at-Risk (VaR)				Expected Shortfall (ES)			
	P25	Median	Mean	P75	P25	Median	Mean	P75
ON	-18.3%	-10.0%	-10.1%	-2.0%	-19.1%	-10.8%	-10.9%	-2.8%
QC	4.9%	8.3%	7.6%	11.1%	4.3%	7.7%	7.0%	10.6%
NY	-155.6%	-133.2%	-132.6%	-107.6%	-157.2%	-134.5%	-133.9%	-109.0%
NE	-191.5%	-164.9%	-169.5%	-141.9%	-193.5%	-166.7%	-171.4%	-143.8%
Total	-1.6%	-1.5%	-1.5%	-1.3%	-2.1%	-1.9%	-1.9%	-1.7%

The table reports regional Value-at-Risk (VaR) and Expected Shortfall (ES) estimates for net low-carbon electricity surplus conditional on cold-wave days, expressed as a share of contemporaneous low-carbon generation. Results are shown at the 10% and 5% VaR levels. Negative values indicate low-carbon deficits requiring imports and/or fossil-fuel generation. Values below -100% indicate deficits exceeding contemporaneous local low-carbon generation.